

Social Media: A Learning Tool in Hei's Physical Education

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Abstract

Near the end of the Covid-19 pandemic, social media are components of educational setting nowadays. It provides an educational platform that often termed as "eLearning" that enables the students and the teachers to be easily connected to communicate that foster meaningful interaction and collaboration in the educational setting environment. The objective of the study was to determine the effects of social media on students' participation in the Higher Educational Institution (HEI) physical education classes in one school in Manila, Philippines, 1st Semester, SY 2022-2023. Colaizzi's method in data analysis in descriptive phenomenology and triangulation used to utilize identifying significant statements from the transcribed data for the formulation of thematic clusters of experiences of the student respondents. There are five (5) important themes developed after the tedious organizing and review of data collected and analyzed: 1) Bridge the Gap, 2) Collaboration, 3) Enhance Creativity, 4) Availability of Resources and 5) Enjoyment, when the themes were combined, the bigger picture of successful meaningful learning experiences of the students have manifested. The researchers, therefore, conclude that the use of the social media is an effective learning tool for the students in HEIs Physical Education.

Keywords: Social media, learning tool, higher education institution, physical education

INTRODUCTION

For more than two years of suffering from social distancing brought about by the Covid-19 pandemic, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines go on blended learning that gave way for the use of social media platforms in the educational setting to continue the students' developmental quest for learning. Joaquin et al (2020) said the response to the needs of 3.5 million tertiary-level students enrolled in approximately 2,400 HEIs, the country have implemented proactive policies that include online learning to bridge the students and teachers educational modality.

Online learning according to University of Arizona staff member (2021) said that the educational institutions are using social media into their classes to engage and support the educational development, whether online or in person are shaping and influencing learning environment of today. Bond et al (2020) agreed that the mobile devices increase the students' participation in and out of the school buildings. Zilles (2019) accounted that social media is having a tremendous impact on modern educational system of today, remember the daily tasks of students before, for commuting going to schools, staying long time in the libraries beyond scheduled classes, carried around heavy backpacks filled with learning materials and books. Those days are over, thanks to the many ways that social media is helping to re-shape the education system. Students are using social media as a way to connect with other classmates in their blended learning classes. Professors are encouraging students to interact on group projects using social media by their digital gadgets and smart phones.

Josep (2022) stated that the concept of traditional education has changed radically. Being physically present in a classroom isn't the only option anymore for meaningful learning experiences because of the rise of the internet and new technologies. The access to a quality education whenever and wherever you are, as long as you can get online will surely connected to the delivery learning modality. This is the new era of educational revolution nowadays.

Digital technology is a part of everyday life. The difficulty of distance communication and learning of yesterday now is just a digital gadget away. Goodman (2022) asserted that it transformed nearly every aspect of the present society in travel, work, shopping, entertainment, in communication and in education are areas that have been changed in recent decades. The use of social media has expanded to include photos, audio, and video, and no longer refers to just words and numbers.

Ansari et al (2020) in their research said that students in higher education are pouring the acceptance of mobile computing devices (cell-phones, smart-phones, and tablets) and play a vital role in the academic performance, physical activity tasks and career enhancement that provide excellent e-learning opportunities to the students for collaboration, and accessing in course contents despite the physical boundary. Haigney (2020) stressed that social media are helpful learning tool, including in the active activities in Physical Education.

Howard Gardner's theory on teaching collaborative skills, providing plenty of group work opportunities, person-person communication, and empathy is very evident in the Physical Education activities of the students in HEI using digital technology (Morenus, 2020).

The perspective of online Physical Education classes are paramount design optimally supplement and support quality in-person programming, taking into consideration the diverse learning and physical activities needs of students (D'Agostino et al, 2021) to be healthy in pandemic times and beyond.

Statement of the Problem

The need for understanding the Physical Education classes in the approaching post Covid-19 pandemic period, for the discovery of the important learning activities of students, the researchers' got involved in the comprehensive analysis and data gathering of the actual experiences of the students in their physical task activities in a HEI in Manila.

The objective of the study is anchored in the phenomenological task of making meaning and revealing the existing features of the different experiences of the students in their PE class task activities.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following:

1. What live experiences using social media shared by the students in their activities in PE?
2. How the experiences contribute to the accomplishments of their task activities?
3. What are the benefits and challenges experienced by the respondents in using the social media as learning tool?
4. What recommendations to be given based on the findings of the study?

Research Paradigm:

Fig_1: Research Paradigm of the study

The Significance of the Study

This study will expand the limited research and find the prevailing reasons why the social media are important to the delivery of effective physical activity learning modality in HEIs PE classes. It will help for the formulation of pedagogical tool which will be beneficial to the following:

School Administrators

They will be able to make strides on the issues regarding problems and concerns of the learners and instructors for blended learning tools modality in PE, assess the issues and concerns so they will be in a better position to address the existing problems in the management of physical activity program.

PE Instructors

They work hand-in-hand to provide a physical education teaching tools, for the adaption of new techniques and innovative activities, and mentor in helping the individuals in their PE classes. Through this study, they will be able to maximize the use of their teaching skills and abilities with social media platform.

Students in HEIs PE

The students will discover the more profound blended learning experiences and increase social media applications competence and skills that important to accomplish physical task activities.

Future Researchers

They will have the opportunity to expand their knowledge on current information in the use of social media for the improvement of teaching of PE and serves as reference for future research.

Methodology

Through Colaizzi's method (1978, and cited also by Praveena K.R. et al, 2021) in data analysis in descriptive phenomenology and triangulation, the researchers' were effectively utilized in identifying significant statements from the transcribed data formulated the meaning clusters which developed the themes experienced of the 100 students randomly selected in 10 different classes of 10 each in a HEI physical education in Manila, Philippines. The researchers' 1) exhaustively review all collected data, 2) carefully extracted, 3) analyzed every significant statements, 4) clusters were formed out of the data analyzed to formulate themes, 5) the themes then tediously described and constantly validated from the data collected, 6) concise themes were formulated, and 7) final validation again on students' experiences from the data collected (if some experiences have not been cited) to best provide a clear description of the benefits and challenges of using social media in HEI physical education.

Results and Discussion

The live experiences, benefits and challenges of using social media applications contributed for the accomplishments of the task activities of the student respondents in this study.

In the process of tedious data gathering, processes and analysis of the live experiences of the students, the researchers utilized five (5) important themes that explained that contributed to participant task activities accomplishments, benefits and challenges of using social media applications. The theme clusters were discussed below:

Bridge the Gap

Most of the student participants have positive regards for social media during their class engagement. According to the participants social media bridges the gap in their learning experiences. They have created their section group chat (gc) messenger, informing each and every one of them, including the instructor for the class messages delivery. Another, for group activities created their own gc for easy communication, exchange of idea and information. They also used personal messaging (pm) and email. Social media meets them via zoom meeting in their synchronous and relay the activities and tasks in asynchronous mode of learning with the use of Red Canvas.

Papademetriou et al (2022) agreed that the use of the social media bridges the gap in the higher education institutions, the impact in enhancing teaching and learning in universities, motivating and supporting the students in their activities.

Collaboration

Groupings in physical education classes were important strategy of instructors to make the students work together in a given physical activity that students in group associated, helped together and interacted while learning.

According to some students, they have divided the task among themselves and have had a group discussion and brain storming, and came up with one agreed activity. They were amazed with the high quality results of working together and received a higher outcome grades.

IBE-UNESCO (2023) stated that collaboration is a process through which learners work together in small groups toward a common goal. It is a learner-centered approach derived from socio-constructivist perspective on learning.

Collaborative learning fosters positive interdependence, individual accountability, and interpersonal skills among students. The instructor's role is not to transmit information, but to serve as a facilitator.

Enhance Creativity

Participants in this study said that social media enhanced the way they did to their own pictures and videos physical activity tasks that challenged their creativity. They were able to made and edited pictures and videos that included basic and advanced filters that enhanced the overall output by adding sound effects, stickers and it allows them to merged pictures, videos, and sounds that they felt emotionally linked each other in the result outcome. Also, unwanted pictures were easily eliminated, made computer editing far more efficient and valuable for students. The students collaged their videos and made it look like they were together did the physical education tasked drills, exercises and dance steps.

Johnson (2019) asserted that creativity is a characteristic trait that fueled the future. Both serve to inspired students in planning and designing learning. Teaching students how to think is more important than teaching students what to think.

According to ELM learning (2021) creative learning is not memorizing information. It's building knowledge and developing skills using creative techniques, rather than dictating how information should be absorbed, it challenges the obvious, the conventional, and the assumed learning like effectively building a comprehension framework. The more learners engage with the process, the longer they retain knowledge and expand their understanding.

Availability of Resources

All students being randomly selected in this study said that everyone have the digital gadget useful in their blended learning and with it the use of social media presents both advantages as well as challenges to them for accessing course contents, pictures, video clips, information, notes, etc. All of the student participants felt that social media were the cheapest and more convenient tool for obtaining relevant information, almost everything in the physical education activities were just a digital gadget away.

According to UAGC Staff Member (2021) Social media promotes self-directed learning, which prepares students to search for answers and make decisions independently. Very useful in physical activity tasks and documentation, these social media skills can be guided and refined to produce better learning outcomes and critical awareness. Social media also allows students more freedom to connect and collaborate beyond the physical learning facilities, which means students anywhere can start to experience the globally connected world.

Enjoyment

The students said that they were challenge to the assigned physical activities but enthusiastically accomplished the task by way of using the social media discovering different settings of taking pictures, shooting, filming, editing, choice of sounds and music that after the finished assignment, with a feeling of a job well done, accomplishment and enjoyment.

Another, the students shared that it allows them together to interact, know each other better with social media thru text messages, calls, share the activity contents and establishing learning rapport.

According to Chukwuere (2021), the conventional lecture-oriented teaching and learning model is changing to social interactive learning norm. Social media platforms' function presents the channel for social interaction among students enjoyment in the learning process and keeps evolving continuously. The students that are actively participated with social media that freely allowed them to contribute, share their feelings and ideas, and get involved in given tasks have accomplished meaningful outcome.

Based on Tus et al (2021) research statistical finding that the respondents' perception of their social media usage significantly affects their academic performance and changing the way students interact, connect, and socialize. As they discovered many things with the usefulness of social media, they enjoyed and spend a significant amount of time on the use of it.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the live experiences of the participants have positive regards for the use of social media by bridging the gap of learning experiences from synchronous and asynchronous mode in their class engagement, having a good rapport collaborating to each classmates, stimulating their creativity skill for the availability of needed material information about a digital gadget away, and to have an enjoying feeling of accomplished outcome task activity.

The researchers, therefore, conclude that the use of the social media is an effective learning tool for the students in HEIs Physical Education, and recommend the use of this technology to enhance the students' relationship, collaboration, stimulate creativity and enjoy accomplishing their task outputs.

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